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**CREATE INSTRUCTIONAL PRESENTATIONS FOR
THE LEARNING PROCESS USING DEMONSTRATION
SOFTWARE.**

Zhumakulov Kamron Shukhrat ugli
student, Navoi State Pedagogical Institute,

Abstract: this article provides an analysis of the state of use of demonstration programs in the educational process and the research of scientists. Explains in detail the process of creating and using educational presentations for the educational process with the help of presenter programs.

Keywords: presentation programs, Power Point, Google Slides, Prezi, Focusky

Introduction. One of the urgent issues of today is choosing an optimal teaching system that can meet the modern requirements in the field of education, computerization of education, and in a broad sense, to inform it, to choose the necessary information for learning, to put it into an educational form. and conveying this information to listeners, mastering them, creating skills and abilities is a requirement of the time.

Currently, the introduction of ICT opportunities in the teaching of various subjects in the education system, among all other fields, is an urgent issue. ICT serves not only to form students' knowledge and skills, but also to develop their personal characteristics and increase their interest in knowledge. In recent years, in many psychological and advanced pedagogic fields, we have seen that the opinions about ICT development of students' knowledge and creative thinking are emphasized. The use of ICT opportunities will help to enrich the range of information provided in the educational process and help students learn it with interest. With the introduction of ICT in the educational process, a new approach to education, characteristic of the modern information environment, began to take shape [1].

Review literature.

Research on the issues of creating educational presentations for the educational process using pedagogical software tools, demonstration programs in the educational system. .Researched by Burdovskaya, Jones, A. M., Craig, R. J., & Amernic, J. H., Kaplan, S., Szabo, A., & Hastings, N.

In the above-mentioned studies, insufficient attention was paid to the use of demonstration programs in the educational process and the process of creating educational presentations for the educational process, as well as the methods and tools of its use. Therefore, the current research is considered important in the training of today's modern personnel.

Research Methodology. New pedagogical and information technologies cannot be separated from each other, because the widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies changes the educational paradigm, and only modern information technologies can ensure the effective use of new pedagogical technologies [3]. One of such modern and pedagogical information technologies is demonstration programs.

Demonstration programs are designed for visual presentation of educational material and for virtualization and visualization of studied laws, interrelationship of objects. Visualization is the creation of real images of these images in a visible state, and virtualization (from the Latin virtualis - probably) is a computer representation of the appearance of objects that take into account the possibility of occurring in certain conditions that do not exist. all edges of this object are taken into account.

Presentation refers to the transfer or presentation of new information to the audience, that is, presentation in the traditional sense is visual material for public speaking[2].

In modern education, it is emphasized that uniformity should be abandoned. Electronic devices and tools for this purpose help a lot in this. Power Point, Google Slides, Prezi, Focusky programs have been developed for this purpose.

Microsoft PowerPoint is a presentation (presentation) graphic program. Such programs allow you to create slides containing text, images, diagrams, graphics, animation effects, sound clips, etc. A presentation created from a sequence of slides can be displayed on a computer screen, video monitors and large screens. There are different versions of Microsoft PowerPoint[7,8,9].

Google Slides is cloud-based, which means you'll need to be online to create your Google Account. After creating your account, Google offers you an offline access feature so you can work on your project offline. When you connect to the Internet again, all work will be synchronized to the live version.

Prezi.com is a modern tool and a new way to create a presentation and demonstrate its capabilities. The service not only has many useful functions, but also has a lot of knowledge that it is ready to transfer to its user.

Focusky makes it easy to create an innovative and professional presentation. From creating backgrounds, editing, adding paths, elements, and animation, Fokusky is a program that brings your presentation to life and perspective.

The advantages of focus are as follows:

- Large selection of templates and themes
- the ability to use various interactive elements such as video, audio, flash, the ability to embed videos from YouTube or Vimeo,
- support for a large number of languages,
- the ability to insert animated objects.

Create a presentation on Prezi.com. Sign up at Prezi.com and let's take a look at creating a themed e-resource.

1. Select the software version you want to use on Prezi.com, then fill out the listing form. When filling out the form, it is required to enter an e-mail address. You

can use your email or Facebook, LinkedIn account to register a free account. This will significantly reduce the registration time, and after logging into your account, you will see my main profile with its main functions.

Figure 1. Practical working window of the Prezi program

2. Select "New Prezi" to create a new presentation. After that, a new window with several templates will appear. By choosing templates for the presentation, the basis of the presentation is built and it is filled with the necessary information. A presentation editor is used for this. Desktop items can be selected by clicking the mouse button. So, all the elements in the template, title, text, images can be edited and changed.

Figure 2. Prezi software presentation template selection dialog box

3. The main tools needed when working with the presentation are located at the top of the window and are divided into three menu groups:

Frames and Arrows menu to define different areas of the form and add new slide views to the presentation;

Figure 3. Prezi Frames and Arrows menu view

Insert menu Insert images, videos and other files to provide the information you need. You can use the KlipArt gallery. You can also add music to your presentation. The most interesting and informative features are the ability to download videos from YouTube and add PowerPoint presentation slides, as well as add audio, image, PDF file and video from the device's internal memory.

Figure 4. Prezi program Insert menu view

Themes menu presentation view can be customized. With this menu, you can choose a different topic at any time. Presentation can be done by equipping or changing the color of an item.

Figure 5. Prezi software Themes menu view

4. At the desired stage of work, you can see how the presentation will be displayed by selecting the Present button on the left side of the window. Although Prezi is a service, it is possible to save the project automatically, in this case, before exiting the editor, you need to press the button below. Anchor points are selectively placed for the base of the presentation. These points are thought of as coordination points, each frame is created based on these points. In the Prezi program, the presentation is given in a guided way. The direction ensures that the presentation moves from one frame to another. Instead of moving in a linear sequence, the route moves in a different order. When the presentation is planned, the camera moves through the sketch. Prezi objects can be zoomed in, zoomed out, and rotated.

5. To save the document, you can first view the page in any way you like. Secondly, the presentation can be launched online. The document can also be saved in PDF format. Another saving method is to save the presentation in standalone view on the computer.

Figure 6. View of the save window in Prezi

Results and Discussion. Today, demonstration programs serve not only in the field of education, but also serve as a basis for business meetings, illustrative speeches and reports, and the presentation of promising or completed projects. Presentations can to some extent guide discussions at conferences or seminars.

Demonstration programs serve to improve the quality of the developing modern education. Preparation systems are presentations, in the process of creating them, the teacher organizes educational, methodological, demonstrative and illustrative materials. Presentations can be used as distance learning courses. Presentations are also useful for the development of educational projects and reports by schoolchildren and students.

Conclusion/Recommendations. According to the findings of the research, animation based on layouts and templates that can include any type of objects (drawings, photos, sounds, videos, tables, etc.) in the educational process with the help of display programs slides and presentations can be created. It is also possible to save in various formats, post presentations on the Internet, print slides and add additional materials for them.

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